

Stereoselective photodimerization and antimicrobial activities of heteroaryl chalcones and their photoproducts

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Abstract : Stereoselective photodimerization of heteroaryl chalcones 1-(furan-2-yl)-3-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (1), 3-phenyl-1-(thiophen-2-yl)prop-2-en-1-one (2) and 3-phenyl-1-(1*H*-pyrrol-2-yl)prop-2-en-1-one (3) has been studied. The heteroaryl chalcones and their photoproducts have also been tested for antimicrobial activity. The heteroaryl chalcones (1-3) showed good activity with minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) in the range of 10–60 µg/mL. The comparison of percentage antimicrobial activities relative to that of standards revealed that the monomeric starting compounds were more active than the dimerization products.

Keywords : Heteroarylchalcones, photodimerization, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Chalcones are among the most widely occurring natural compounds with various biological activities such as antiinflammatory, antitumour, antibacterial, antituberculous, antiviral, antiprotozoal, gastroprotective and others¹⁻⁹.

In the last few years, the isolation of some cyclobutane derivatives of natural compounds from *Agelas spectrum*, *Agelas conifera*, *Combretum albopunctatum* and *Goniothalamus thwaitesii* have been reported¹⁰⁻¹². The synthesis of cyclobutane ring is one of the most studied reactions due to dimerization of α,β -unsaturated carbonyl compounds in particular of 1,3-diaryl-2-propen-1-one

(chalcones)¹³⁻²¹ in organic photochemistry. Analogous to these dimers of chalcones, three new dimers (4-6) of heteroaryl chalcones were synthesized stereoselectively in the current study.

The heteroaryl chalcones (1-3) have been prepared with the known procedure²²⁻²⁶, according to the route indicated in Scheme 1. These heteroaryl chalcones, when exposed to UV light (125 W low pressure Hg lamp), are converted to the respective cyclobutanes 4-6 as major products, with the yields (chromatographed products) of 52, 59 and 49% respectively (Scheme 2). The minor products of these reactions were less than 5% which were not characterized.

Scheme 1. Preparation of heteroaryl chalcones.

Scheme 2. Photodimerization of heteroaryl chalcones.

Materials and methods :

Acetophenone, 2-acylfurane, 2-acylthiophene and 2-acylpyrrole were purchased from Lancaster and used without further purification. The solvents (chloroform, *n*-hexane, ethanol and methanol) used were of analytical grade. The compounds 1-3 were prepared by literature method²²⁻²⁶.

Photodimerization of 1-3 in solution :

Solutions of compounds 1-3 in ethanol were exposed to UV light (125 W low pressure Hg lamp). The progress of the reaction was followed by silica gel TLC (hexane-benzene). The reaction completed in 32, 30 and 35 h respectively. The solutions were evaporated and the residues were purified by column chromatography (column

length 30 cm, diameter 2 cm) on silica gel (25 g, Merck, 230-400 mesh). The columns were eluted successively with the following solvent and solvent mixtures : hexane, hexane-benzene, benzene-ethyl acetate, benzene-methanol. Fractions (10-15 ml each) were collected and monitored by TLC. The product 4 were obtained from fractions 6-9 (1.04 g, 52% yield, hexane-benzene) and 5 from fractions 5-6 (1.18 g, 59% yield, hexane) and 6 from fractions 9-12 (0.98 g, 49% yield, benzene-ethyl acetate).

(3,4-Diphenylcyclobutane-1,2-diyl)bis(furan-2-ylmethanone) (4) :

Yellowish amorphous solid, m.p. 103 °C; ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 300 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 60 MHz) δ

Table 1. Chemical shifts of dimeric products 4, 5 and 6

X = O (4), S (5), NH (6)

Position of H/C	Product 4		Product 5		Product 6	
	δ_H	δ_C	δ_H	δ_C	δ_H	δ_C
1, 2	4.50 (m)	48.45	4.56 (m)	48.54	4.77 (m)	47.74
3, 4	4.14 (m)	47.70	3.95 (m)	47.57	4.48 (m)	46.90
CO	—	186.82	—	191.82	—	191.82
1''	—	152.0	—	143.0	—	132.0
2'	6.90 (d)	118.0	7.44 (d)	133.0	6.35 (d)	117.0
3'	6.98-7.08 (dd)	112.0	6.90 (dd)	128.7	7.05 (dd)	111.0
4'	7.20 (d)	147.0	7.75 (d)	134.0	7.65 (d)	125.0
Phenyl	7.14-7.18 (m)	142, 129, 128.3, 127.9	7.3-7.42 (m)	1.42, 129, 128.3, 127	7.26-7.40 (m)	140, 127-128.3
NH	—	—	—	—	9.6	—

ppm are presented in Table 1. FAB mass m/z : 396 [M^+], 368, 329, 301, 289, 217, 198 (monomer peak), 197, 121, 115, 105, 95; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3028 (arom. CH str.), 2931, 2836 (aliph. CH str.), 1645 (C=O str.), 1561, 1464 (arom. C=C str.), 390 (aliph. CH bend.), 1272 (O-C str.), 768, 746 (C-H bend. in aryl ring) (Found : C, 78.75; H, 5.12. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4$: C, 78.78; H, 5.05%).

(3,4-Diphenylcyclobutane-1,2-diyl)bis(thiophen-2-ylmethanone) (**5**) :

Grayish white crystalline solid, m.p. 105 °C; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) and ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 60 MHz) are presented in Table 1. FAB mass m/z : 429 [$M+1$], 428 [M^+], 351, 317, 305, 249, 227, 214 (monomer peak), 180, 111, 103; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3103, 3085 (arom. CH str.), 2964, 2925 (aliph. CH str.), 1642 (C=O str.), 1549, 1518, 1452, 1411–1450 (arom. C=C str.), 1356, 1302 (aliph. CH bend.), 1156, 1060 (C-CO-C str. and bend.), 991, 967, 639, 753, 727 (out-of-plane arom. CH bend.), 610 cm^{-1} (C-S str.) (Found : C, 72.82; H, 4.70; S, 14.98. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$: C, 72.89; H, 4.67; S, 14.95%).

(3,4-Diphenylcyclobutane-1,2-diyl)bis(1H-pyrrol-2-ylmethanone) (**6**) :

Light yellowish amorphous solid, m.p. 141 °C; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3 , 300 MHz) and ^{13}C NMR (CDCl_3 , 60 MHz) are presented in Table 1. FAB mass m/z : 395 [$M+1$], 394 [M^+], 328, 304, 300, 272, 215, 197 (monomer peak), 169, 131, 94; FT-IR (cm^{-1}) : 3298 (NH str.), 3010 (arom. and heteroarom. CH str.), 2924, 2838 (aliph. CH str.), 1640 (C=O str.), 1548 (NH bend.), 1500, 1410 (arom. and heteroarom. C=C ring str.), 1350 (aliph. CH bend.), 1290 (C-N str.), 1110, 1050 (C-O str.), 950, 850, 753, 700 cm^{-1} (out-of-plane arom. CH bend) (Found : C, 79.20, H, 5.62; N, 7.15. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$: C, 79.18; H, 5.68; N, 7.10%).

Results and discussion

Scheme 2 illustrates the synthetic approach chosen for the preparation of dimerization products of 1-(furan-2-yl)-3-phenylprop-2-en-1-one (**1**), 3-phenyl-1-(thiophen-2-yl)prop-2-en-1-one (**2**) and 3-phenyl-1-(1H-pyrrol-2-yl)prop-2-en-1-one (**3**).

The most noticeable feature of the structural characterization of **1**, **2** and **3** chalcones is the assignment of the proton resonances of their α,β -unsaturated moiety, which

was made by a careful analysis of their ^1H and 2D COSY NMR. On the basis of the vicinal coupling constants ($^3J_{\text{H}\alpha\text{-H}\beta}$ 16.4/15.8/15.8 Hz, respectively), the *trans* configuration of these two protons is suggested.

Two symmetrical multiplets (AA'BB') at δ_{H} 4.50 (δ_{C} 48.45)/ δ_{H} 4.14 (δ_{C} 47.70) for compound **4**, at δ_{H} 4.56 (δ_{C} 48.54)/ δ_{H} 3.95 (δ_{C} 47.57) for compound **5** and at δ_{H} 4.77 (δ_{C} 47.74)/ δ_{H} 4.48 (δ_{C} 46.90) for compound **6** were observed for the cyclobutyl proton in ^1H NMR spectra. Simulation of these NMR patterns has allowed the calculation of the coupling constants of the cyclobutyl protons ($J_{\text{AA}'}$ = 6.6/6.1, J_{AB} = 4.1/4.2, $J_{\text{AB}'}$ = 1.5/1.9, $J_{\text{BB}'}$ = 6.6/6.1, respectively) for compound **4** and **6** and ($J_{\text{AA}'}$ = 9.2/9.0, J_{AB} = 5.2, $J_{\text{AB}'}$ = not detected, $J_{\text{BB}'}$ = 8.6, respectively) for compound **5**³²⁻⁴². The values of these coupling constants and ^1H and ^{13}C NMR patterns of the cyclobutyl moieties of compounds **4** and **6** suggest that the formation of cyclobutane ring occurs by *cis* head to head junction to give β -truxinic structure^{32,33}, different from the earlier studies^{32-34,43-48}. The close similarity of the ^1H and ^{13}C NMR patterns of the cyclobutyl moieties of compound **5** with δ -truxinic structure strongly suggests that the formation of cyclobutane ring occurs by anti head to head junction in compound **5**³³⁻³⁸.

The positive FAB mass spectra gave M^+ at m/z 390 (100) for **4**, at m/z 428 (100) for **5** and at m/z 394 (100) for **6**, which were consistent with the molecular formula to be $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4$ for **4**, $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_2\text{S}_2$ for **5** and $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$ for **6** requiring dimeric structure (Scheme 3). FAB mass showed a typical chalcone fragmentation with a fragment ions for **4** at m/z 198 (chalcone monomer, $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2$), for **5** at m/z 214 (chalcone monomer, $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{OS}$) and for **6** at m/z 197 (chalcone monomer, $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}$).

The compounds **4-6** were characterized on the basis of spectral data evaluations (^1H , ^{13}C , ^1H - ^1H COSY NMR, FT-IR, UV-Vis and FAB Mass), whose results were in agreement with the proposed structures (Table 1). Based upon the above observation, the complete chemical shift assignments for **4**, **5** and **6** were deduced and are shown in Table 1. Compounds **4**, **5** and **6** were thus shown to be (1 α ,2 α)-di-(2-thienoyl)-(3 β ,4 β)-di-(4-phenyl)cyclobutane (**4**), (1 β ,2 α)-di-(2-oxenoyl)-(3 β ,4 α)-di-(4-phenyl)-cyclobutane (**5**) and (1 α ,2 α)-di-(2-azaenoyl)-(3 β ,4 β)-di-(4-phenyl)cyclobutane (**6**).

Antimicrobial activity assessment : All test micro-

Table 2. Antimicrobial activity of heteroaryl chalcone (1-3) and their photoproduct (4-6) against bacteria

Sl. no.	Bacteria	Diameter of zone of inhibition in mm (μg)					
		1	4	2	5	3	6
1.	<i>Citrobactor sruendi</i>	11 (10)	5	9 (50)	5	9 (40)	5
2.	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	7 (20)	9	8 (10)	9	8 (20)	9
3.	<i>Proteus vulgaris</i>	15 (20)	7	11 (40)	5	5 (20)	5
4.	<i>Bacillus megaterium</i>	11 (20)	5	13 (20)	9	13 (20)	5
5.	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	5 (10)	5	5 (10)	5	7 (30)	5
6.	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	5 (10)	7	5 (10)	6	7 (40)	5
7.	<i>Salmonella typhi</i>	5 (10)	6	7 (10)	9	7 (40)	8
8.	<i>Micrococcus luteus</i>	11 (20)	5	9 (10)	5	5 (20)	5
9.	<i>Serratia marcescens</i>	5 (10)	5	9 (50)	5	9 (20)	10

Table 3. Antimicrobial activity of heteroaryl chalcone (1-3) and their photoproduct (4-6) against fungi

Sl. no.	Fungi	Diameter of inhibition zone in mm (μg)					
		1	4	2	5	3	6
1.	<i>Aspergillus oryzae</i>	7 (40)	5	9 (10)	5	9 (30)	5
2.	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	11 (30)	5	7 (20)	5	9 (60)	5
3.	<i>Fusarium moniliformae</i>	9 (20)	9	9 (10)	5	9 (60)	5
4.	<i>Candida albicans</i>	7 (20)	5	9 (40)	5	7 (10)	5

organisms were obtained from Department of Microbiology, Vikram University, Ujjain and were as follows : *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Citrobactor sruendi*, *Bacillus megaterium*, *Proteus vulgaris*, *Micrococcus luteus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Candida albicans* (human pathogen), *Aspergillus niger* (mould), *Aspergillus oryzae* and *Fusarium moniliformae*.

The antimicrobial activities of the substances were tested by disc diffusion^{27,28} and poisoned food technique^{29,30} quantitatively in high media muller hinton agar and potato dextrose agar. The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) values ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) were determined³¹ and defined as the lowest concentrations that showed no growth of micro-organisms. Ampicillin and fluconazole were used as standard antibacterial and antifungal drugs respectively. Rectified ethanol was used as solvent control.

The antimicrobial activity of all the compounds (1-6) was determined (Tables 2 and 3). The activities of the synthesized compounds were investigated by disc diffusion and potato dextrose assays. The compounds 1-6 showed antimicrobial activity against Gram-positive bacteria, Gram-negative bacteria, fungi and yeast. The com-

pounds showed better antimicrobial activity against Gram-positive bacteria compared to Gram-negative bacteria. Compounds 1-3 exhibited broad spectrum antimicrobial activity. These three compounds were active against all test organisms except for *E. coli*, *P. aeruginosa*, *S. typhi* and *S. marcescens*. The MIC value for test micro-organisms were between 10–40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Compounds 4 and 5 were specifically effective against *B. megaterium*, *P. vulgaris* with the MIC values of 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ respectively. The comparison of percentage antimicrobial activities relative to that of streptomycin and fluconazole revealed that the monomeric starting compounds were more active than the dimers. Compounds 1 and 2 were found to be highly effective antimicrobial agents. A little increase was observed in the antimicrobial activity of the monomer against *K. pneumoniae* and *S. typhi*. The antimicrobial bacterial and antifungal activities of the heteroaryl chalcones both make them potential agents for the cure of bacterial and fungal infections.

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